

STUDY ON BENDING FRACTURE MECHANISM OF STAMPABLE SHEET
BY FREQUENCY ANALYSIS OF ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

The stampable sheet used in this study is composed of polypropylene resin and chopped strand glass fiber. The various stampable sheets, which had four kinds of glass fiber length, four kinds of fiber content and four kind of fiber dispersion, were prepared. The specimens were molded from these molding materials and were investigated in order to clarify the fracture mechanism in detail. An AE sensor was attached on a test piece. The forty AE waves were measured during one bending test. Then, these AE waves were analyzed with a FFT, and each power spectrum was calculated. Consequently the characteristic frequency corresponding to the each fracture patterns were revealed. That is to say, it is considered that the frequency of 65kHz is generated from the breakage of the matrix (PP), the frequency of 85kHz is generated from the breakage of a glass fiber, the frequency of 105kHz is generated from the frictional slip between the glass fiber and the matrix, the frequency of 135kHz is generated from the slip of the glass fiber in a chopped strand bundle, and the frequency of 160kHz is generated from the interface debonding of the glass fiber from the matrix. Some of them were confirmed experimentally with tensile tests in a SEM.

KEYWORDS: Stampable sheet; Glass fiber; Polypropylene resin; Failure mechanism; Acoustic Emission.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently stampable sheets have been more used because molding parts can be easily gotten by compression molding. So many kinds of stampable sheets have been developed. However the stampable sheet most commonly used is

glass fiber reinforced polypropylene resin sheet. In fibrous composites such as the stampable sheet, the fiber length, the fiber orientation, and the interface strength between fiber and matrix affect the strength of molded parts. Thus the fracture mechanism of the composite is more complicated than homogeneous materials. It is reported that the frequency analysis of AE (Acoustic Emission) is effective in order to clarify the fracture mechanism of composites.[1, 2] The AE is an elastic wave generated with the deformation and a crack propagation in the material. The sources of the AE in the fracture of the composite seem the fiber breakage, the fiber pull-out and the interface debonding between the matrix and the fiber. In the real fracture, these fracture patterns seem to be combined. Previously Suzuki et.al. [3 ~ 6] and Komai et.al. [7, 8] have investigated the fracture mechanism by the frequency analysis of AE. They got the effective results by measuring AE event count, AE event rate, AE energy, AE amplitude and frequency spectrum in the tensile test of unidirectional FRP. However they haven't gotten the exact relation between the fracture pattern and the frequency of the power spectrum. So, in present report, we investigated the various kinds of the stampable sheets in the bending test by analyzing the frequency of AE. Namely, these are the stampable sheets of different fiber length, different fiber content and different fiber dispersion. The FFT analyses of the measured AE waves during a bending test were carried out. Then, we investigated the difference of fracture pattern during a bending test.

2. MATERIAL AND PROCEDURES

2.1 Test materials The stampable sheets used are composed of polypropylene resin as a matrix and chopped strand glass fiber as a reinforcement. Table 1 shows their composition. All the stampable sheets were compressed into a sheet by the hydraulic press machine whose maximum load is 50ton. The molded part dimension is $500 \times 500 \times 4$ mm. The stampable sheets of No.1 ~ 4 in the material number are the different fiber length of 3, 6, 13, 25mm, those of No.5 ~ 8 are the different fiber content of 20, 30, 40, 50% and those of No.9 ~ 12 are the different dispersion of A, B, C, D. The fiber dispersion shows the degree of unfastening of the glass fiber bundle. To put it simply, it is shown as the product of the mixer revolutionary speed and mixing time. The chopped fibers are more unfastened according to the order of A to D, and the fiber dispersion D is the most unfastened condition. The specimens were machined into the size of $80 \times 10 \times 4$ mm. In order to compare with them, a polypropylene resin sheet and a glass fiber plate were also used.

2.2 Test method Figure 1 shows the schematic apparatus of the bending

Table 1. Composition of stampable sheets

No.	Fiber bundle	Fiber length mm	Fiber contents %	Fiber dispersion* (Mixing number)
1		3		
2	800	6	40	(C)
3		13		
4		25		
5			20	
6	135	13	30	(C)
7			40	
8			50	
9				A (475)
10	135	13	40	B (1425)
11				C (5700)
12				D (2000)

* Chopped strand in the state of D is more unfastened than that in the state of A.

test. The radius of the loading nose is 5mm, the radius of the supports is 2mm and the support span is 60mm. The rate of the crosshead motion is 1.5mm/min. An AE sensor was attached on the specimen with wax and the AE were detected during the bending test. AE signals were amplified through 100kHz high pass filter by the AE tester (NF CIRCUIT DESIGN BLOCK Co., NF9501) and transmitted to the FFT (ADVANTEST Co., TR9407). These signals were analyzed and calculated the power spectrum. The AE sensor (NF CIRCUIT DESIGN BLOCK Co., AE-900S-WB) is a wide range type of 100k ~ 1MHz. The fracture surfaces were observed by a SEM. The AE tester has maximum input of 50mV_{p-p}, maximum output of 1V_{p-p} and input sensibility of 0.5mV. The FFT analyzer has the maximum frequency range of 1MHz and the power spectrum was determined from the measured AE waves. The AE wave and the power spectrum on the CRT display were recorded photographically. During one bending test,

Figure 1. Schematic apparatus of bending test for analyzing AE.

more than 40 photographs were taken. The load was measured with the dynamometer under the supports during the bending test. One example of measured AE wave and the power spectrum is shown in Figure 2. The measured AE doesn't always occur from only one event but is possible to occur from more than two events. Then the estimation method of the power spectrum is done as follows: Firstly some threshold level is determined so that about ten higher peaks than the threshold level can be selected. For example in Figure 2 the threshold level is determined -50dB. Next, the frequency band is divided every 25kHz and the peaks were classified in which frequency band the peak locate. In Figure 2, the peaks were located in the range of 50 ~ 75kHz, 75 ~ 100kHz, 100 ~ 125kHz, 125 ~ 150kHz, 150 ~ 175kHz, 175 ~ 200kHz, 275 ~ 300kHz. Moreover the power in the longitudinal axis was divided every -10dB. The degree of a peak is determined to be one when the peak located between the threshold level and higher level 10dB than that, and the degree of a peak is determined to be two when the peak located in the upper region. And the degree increases every 10dB. Then the degree of a peak from the threshold level is represented numerically against all the 40 AE waves. In case of Figure 2, the estimation of the AE power spectrum is shown in Table 2. The number of the degree of the peak in the power spectrum (Nd) is obtained by summation from the beginning of the bending test to the end, and this is shown in the figure of the total histogram. Besides, the AE waves were divided into 4 regions according to the proceeding of the bending fracture, and the histogram is shown respectively in the region I, II, III, IV.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 AE wave analysis of polypropylene and glass First, the AE waves of the polypropylene resin as the matrix and the glass fiber as the reinforcement were analyzed. Both the polypropylene resin sheet and the glass plate generated the AE in the last stage of the bending fracture. The AE at that

Table 2. Estimation of power spectrum peak

Frequency kHz	Degree of power spectrum peak
50 ~ 75	1
75 ~ 100	3
100 ~ 125	2
125 ~ 150	2
150 ~ 175	1
175 ~ 200	1
275 ~ 300	1

Figure 2. An example of AE wave (upper) and frequency power spectrum (lower).

Table 3. Frequency of maximum power spectrum of polypropylene and glass

Time μ s	1st time		2nd time	
	PP	Glass	PP	Glass
0 ~ 400	152.5	85.0	45.0	85.0
400 ~ 800	65.0	End	62.5	End
800 ~ 1200	65.0		127.5	
1200 ~ 1600	67.5		65.0	
1600 ~ 2000	65.0		65.0	
2000 ~ 2400	65.0		65.0	
2400 ~ 2800	65.0		End	
2800 ~ 3200	65.0			
3200 ~ 3600	End			

moment were measured. Table 3 shows the frequency of the maximum peak in power spectrum of PP and glass. However the breakage of the glass was so fast that we could measure for only 400 μ s. According to the Table 3, the frequency of AE wave in the breakage of PP is around 65kHz, and that of the glass is around 85kHz.

3.2 AE wave analysis of stampable sheet of various fiber dispersion

Next, the stampable sheets of various fiber dispersion were investigated. Figure 3 shows the SEM photographs of the fracture surface in the stampable sheets of the different fiber dispersion. In the fiber dispersion A, the fibers weren't unfastened enough and were contained in the state of the

(a) Fiber dispersion A

(b) Fiber dispersion D

Figure 3. SEM photographs of fracture surface.

Figure 4. Frequency analysis of AE in fiber dispersion A.
 (1) Distribution of Nd
 (2) Load-displacement curve
 (3) Distribution of Nd in various regions
 (4) Frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum

fiber bundle. However, in the fiber dispersion D, the fibers were unfastened and contained in the state of a monofilament.

Figure 4 shows the results of the AE wave analysis in the stampable sheet of the fiber dispersion A. This includes the total histogram of the degree of the peak Nd in the bending test, the representative histogram in the region I, II, III, IV and the frequency of maximum peak in the power spectrum of the region I, II, III, IV. Moreover, the load-deflection curve is also shown in Figure 4. In the fiber dispersion A, There are so wide distribution of 75 ~ 150kHz, and the distribution profile is similar among the region I, II, III, IV. That is to say, the fracture pattern seems to be almost similar every stage of fracture.

Figure 5 shows the results of the AE wave analysis in the stampable sheet of the fiber dispersion B. There are so wide distribution of 50 ~ 150kHz in the fiber dispersion B. Especially the distribution of 125 ~ 150kHz is the most. As the proceeding of the region I, II, III, IV, that is to say, as approaching to the maximum load in the bending test, the fracture with the frequency of around 135kHz occurs several times. If the frequency generated at the fiber breakage is assumed to be equal to the frequency of the glass

Figure 5. Frequency analysis of AE in fiber dispersion B.
 (1) Distribution of Nd
 (2) Load-displacement curve
 (3) Distribution of Nd in various regions
 (4) Frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum

plate (85kHz), this 135kHz is generated from any other cause. In the fiber dispersion B, the fiber bundle is not unfastened enough, so this frequency is considered to be generated from the slip of the glass fiber in the fiber bundle.

Figure 6 shows the results of the AE wave analysis in the stampable sheet of the fiber dispersion C. There are so wide distribution of 75 ~ 150kHz in the fiber dispersion C. As the proceeding of the region I, II, III, IV, the distribution of 75 ~ 100kHz and 125 ~ 150kHz increases, and in the frequency of the maximum peak, the number of around 85 and 135kHz increases. But the number of around 105kHz decreased conversely. Considering from this point, the frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix decreases, and the fiber breakage and the fiber slip in the fiber bundle increase as the proceeding of bending.

Figure 7 shows the results of the AE wave analysis in the stampable sheet of the fiber dispersion D. The distribution concentrated to the frequency of 50 ~ 150kHz in the fiber dispersion D. Especially the frequency of 75 ~ 100kHz, and 100 ~ 125kHz generated the most. In the region I, the frequency of 75 ~ 100kHz generated several times and the maximum peak is

Figure 6. Frequency analysis of AE in fiber dispersion C.
 (1) Distribution of Nd
 (2) Load-displacement curve
 (3) Distribution of Nd in various regions
 (4) Frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum

around 85kHz. In the early stage of the bending test, the fiber breakage occurs because of the tensile stress transmitted from the matrix. In the region IV, the distribution of the frequency of 100 ~ 125kHz is the most and the maximum peak of around 105kHz generated the most. In the fiber dispersion D, the fiber are in the most unfastened state, and so the fibers have the large area of the interface to the matrix. Considering from this point, the maximum peak of around 105kHz seems to be the fiber slip from the matrix because of the weak bonding. In the region IV, the distribution of the frequency of 105 ~ 175kHz is more than any other fiber dispersion stampable sheet. Moreover, in the region II, III, IV, the maximum peak is the frequency of around 160kHz. This seems to be the AE wave generated from the entire interface debonding between the fiber and the matrix.

So far, as the change of the fiber dispersion A, B, C, D, the fibers of the fiber bundle become unfastened. So, in the fiber dispersion A, the adhesion among fibers is tight and the various fractures occur. In the fiber dispersion B, the adhesion in the fiber bundle is more or less loose. Then the fiber slip occurred in the fiber bundle as the proceeding of the fracture. In the fiber dispersion C, the fibers become to have large

Figure 7. Frequency analysis of AE in fiber dispersion D.

- (1) Distribution of Nd
- (2) Load-displacement curve
- (3) Distribution of Nd in various regions
- (4) Frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum

interface to the matrix because they are unfastened. So, the the fiber breakage occurs because of the tension from the matrix. The frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix decrease and the fiber slip in the fiber bundle increase as the proceeding of bending. In the fiber dispersion D, the fiber breakage occurs much and the frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix occurs. Moreover, the interface debonding of the fiber from the matrix occurs too.

3.3 The AE wave analysis in stampable sheet of various fiber length

The similar AE wave analysis was carried out to the stampable sheets of the various fiber length. These stampable sheets have the 800 fibers in the fiber bundle and the fiber is not unfastened enough. So the fibers don't have the large interface of the matrix. The fracture of the frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix didn't occur much, and the fracture proceeded with the fiber slip in the fiber bundle. In the fiber length of 3, 6mm, the fracture with the fiber breakage didn't occur much, and the fracture proceeded with the fiber slip in the fiber bundle. In the fiber length of 13, 25mm, the fracture proceeded with the fiber breakage from the early stage of bending. The fracture proceed with the fiber slip in the

fiber bundle as the increase of the deflection.

3.4 AE wave analysis in stampable sheet of various fiber content

The similar AE wave analysis was carried out to the stampable sheets of the various fiber content. As the increase of the fiber content, the contact state between matrix and fiber doesn't become good because of the bad mixing of fiber. In the fiber content of 20%, the fibers have the large area of interface with matrix, so the fiber breakage occurred as the proceeding of the bending. However in the fiber content of 30 and 40%, many fibers become to contact with the other fibers. Then, the fracture with the fiber slip against the other fiber becomes to occurs. In the fiber content of 50%, fiber breakage occurs very much.

3.5 Micro tensile test in SEM The fracture process was observed with the micro tensile experimental apparatus in the SEM. The rate of the crosshead motion is $2\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. The AE was measured at the same time. Figure 8 shows the photographs of the crack growth in the stampable sheet of the

Figure 8. SEM photographs of tensile fracture state and frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum. (Fiber dispersion B)

Figure 9. SEM photographs of tensile fracture state and frequency distribution of maximum peak in power spectrum. (Fiber dispersion D)

fiber dispersion B. According to the photographs (a), (b), (c), the fibers in the crack were stretched. The fiber was observed to break because of the tension and then to be pulled out from the fiber bundle. At that moment, the maximum peaks of the AE wave were the frequency of around 85kHz and around 135kHz. Considering from this point, the AE wave generated with the fiber slip in the fiber bundle is around 135kHz.

Figure 9 shows the photographs of the crack growth in the fiber dispersion D. According to the photographs (a), (b), (c), the fiber in the crack slips in the matrix and are pulled out from the matrix. At that moment the maximum peak of the AE wave was the frequency of around 105kHz. Considering from this point, the AE wave generated with the frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix is around 105kHz.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The various kinds of the stampable sheets were investigated by analyzing the

frequency of the AE in the bending test. The characteristic frequency corresponding to the each fracture patterns could be revealed. The results obtained are as follows:

- (1) The breakage of the matrix is the frequency of around 65kHz.
- (2) The breakage of the glass fiber is the frequency of around 85kHz.
- (3) The frictional slip between the fiber and the matrix is the frequency of around 105kHz.
- (4) The fiber slip in the fiber bundle is the frequency of around 135kHz.
- (5) The interface debonding of the fiber from the matrix is the frequency of around 160kHz.

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REFERENCES

1. T.Kishi and M.shiba, Jour.Jpn.Soc.Comp.Mater., 10 (3), 102 (1984).
2. T.Sagawa, Jour.Jpn.Soc.Comp.Mater., 15 (3), 104 (1989).
3. M.Suzuki, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 53 (492A), 1459 (1987).
4. M.Suzuki, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 55 (513A), 1081 (1989).
5. M.Suzuki, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 56 (525A), 1030 (1990).
6. M.Suzuki, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 56 (525A), 1036 (1990).
7. K.Komai, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 54 (505A), 1677 (1988).
8. K.Komai, et. al., Trans.Jpn.Soc.Mech.Eng., 56 (528A), 1792 (1990).

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